

Studies on the Biuret Reaction of Barbitone

M. A. Beg, A. A. Khan and S. M. Ashraf

Biuret reaction of barbitone was studied by employing amperometric and polarographic techniques. Due to the insolubility of barbitone in water, it was dissolved in 0.5*M* caustic potash. The electrode reaction is a one electron transfer process. One copper atom has been found to be combined with four barbitone molecules.

Barbitone has been found to react with copper to give a violet complex in alcoholic medium (Rising and Co-workers¹). On the basis of chemical analysis the violet complex has been assigned the formula $\text{Na}_2\text{Cu}(\text{barbitone})_4$. Besides, it also reacts with a number of metal ions and is used for analytical purposes². The compositions of the complexes have been studied mainly by chemical analysis. For the last few years, we have been using the electrochemical methods especially the polarographic technique for studying the biuret reaction³, and this paper is a continuation of the same series.

EXPERIMENTAL

Barbitone (E. Merck) was dissolved in two different concentrations of KOH (0.5*M* and 0.8*M*) to give a 0.5*M* solution. Copper sulphate of 0.2*M* concentration was obtained by dissolving B.D.H. Analar sample. Potassium nitrate which was used as the supporting electrolyte was also of A.R. grade and a stock solution of 2.0*M* was prepared. Methyl red (B.D.H.) in the concentration of 0.001% was used as the maximum suppressor.

Polarographic measurements were made with Fisher Electrode with Lange's Multiflex Galvanometer MGF 2 in the external circuit. Double distilled mercury was used for the dropping mercury electrode and saturated calomel electrode was used as the reference electrode. Amperometric titrations between barbitone and copper sulphate were also carried out with the same assembly. The temperature was maintained at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$; oxygen free nitrogen was used for deaeration.

A number of polarograms at different concentrations of barbitone and KOH were drawn and typical ones are depicted in Fig. 1. Typical amperometric titration curves are also shown in Fig. 2.

1. M. M. Rising, R. C. Johnson, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, **80**, 710.
2. Jack Schubert and Arthur Lindenbom, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 3529-32; 1957, **79**, 5864-70; Conard Berggardth, *Finska Kemistsamfundets Medd.*, 1949, **58**, 88-99.
3. A. A. Khan and W. U. Malik, *Naturwiss.*, 1959, **46**, 376; *J. Polarographic Society*, U. K., (1959), No. 2; *Zeit. Phys. Chem. New Folge*, 1960, **25**, 1/2, 130.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Barbitone reacts with copper ions in presence of alkali to give a violet compound having a rather low solubility. The reaction is similar to other biuret reactions and can be represented by the following general equation

The reaction at the dropping mercury electrode may be represented as

and the half wave potential is given by

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = E_0 + 0.059, \log K \frac{k_a}{k_c} - p \cdot 0.0591 \log C_B$$

Where E_0 is the standard potential for the half reaction taking place at the electrode, p is the number of barbitone molecules per atom of bound copper, C_B is the concentration of the barbitone; K is the equilibrium constant and k_a and k_c are proportional to the square roots of the diffusion co-efficient of the metal in amalgam and the complex metal ion respectively.

FIG. 3

The involvement of one electron in the electrode reaction was calculated by Tom's method as $E_{\frac{1}{2}}^3 - E_{\frac{1}{2}} = .065$. On plotting curves between $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and \log concentration of barbitone, (Fig. 3) a straight line with a slope of 0.24 was obtained showing thereby that four molecules of barbitone are combined with one atom of copper. The structure may be represented in the following way

Dissociation constant of the complex was calculated by using the equation

$$(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c - (E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s = 0.0591 \log K_c - p \cdot 0.0591 \log C_B$$

where K_c is the dissociation constant of the complex and $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c$ and $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s$ are the half wave potentials of the complex and simple metal ions respectively. The mean was equal to 15×10^{-2} at 25° .

These results confirm the work of Rising and Co-workers on the problem.

The amperometric titrations (Fig. 2) also support the polarographic results. The break is observed at a ratio of one atom of copper to 4 molecules of barbitone in confirmation of the above results and formula of the complex.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY,
ALIGARH, INDIA.

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